

PREDICTING JOB BURNOUT AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG THE HEALTHCARE WORKFORCE

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Predicting Job Burnout and Job Satisfaction among the Healthcare Workforce

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine predictors influencing the level of job burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare workers at Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC), focusing on organizational climate, organizational commitment levels, and personnel profiles. Through a descriptive-inferential research approach and questionnaire administration among 314 respondents, data were collected and analyzed using frequencies, means, and multiple regression analysis. The study was conducted during FY 2023–2024. Key findings revealed diversified demographic profile of participants, a strong organizational climate, high organizational commitment, concerning job burnout levels, and satisfactory job satisfaction aspects with room for improvement in terms of operating conditions. The analysis unveiled significant relationships of the independent variables to have a predictive impact on job burnout. Higher job satisfaction was found to reduce burnout whereas higher pay, a demanding organizational climate and a strong normative commitment increased burnout. Affective and normative commitment, along with rewards and recognition, increased personal accomplishment, and type of hospital service, were positively associated with job satisfaction. This indicates that employees who demonstrated strong loyalty and belonging, have received rewards and recognition, and had a sense of achievement in their work reported higher levels of job satisfaction. Conversely, emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and gender exhibited negative beta coefficients. This suggests that lower levels of burnout and certain gender identities were associated with higher job satisfaction. A model, developed from these results to alleviate job burnout and enhance job satisfaction for healthcare workers, was suggested for pilot testing and possible implementation in specific units before hospital-wide adoption.

Keywords: *job burnout, job satisfaction, healthcare workforce*

Introduction

In the high-pressure realm of healthcare, dedicated professionals are crucial for delivering quality care to patients and maintaining overall well-being. However, healthcare work comes with its own set of challenges, including long hours, emotional strain, and heavy workloads, which contribute to high levels of job burnout and decreased job satisfaction among healthcare workers (Maslach et al., 1996; Shanafelt et al., 2015). These issues not only affect individual well-being but also have negative repercussions on the healthcare system as a whole, leading to reduced productivity, increased absenteeism, and higher turnover rates (Aiken et al., 2005; West et al., 2014).

One essential factor that plays a significant role in employee well-being and performance is the organizational climate within a healthcare facility. Elements like leadership style, communication patterns, work-life balance, and employee recognition collectively shape the organizational climate and greatly influence employee morale, commitment, and engagement (Paredes, 2023). A positive organizational climate characterized by transparent communication, supportive leadership, and fair recognition has been associated with higher organizational commitment, leading to increased job satisfaction, reduced burnout, and improved patient care (Jay, 2023; Laschinger et al., 2015; Shanafelt et al., 2016).

A study conducted by Milieu Insight and Intellect highlighted that 52% of Filipino employees experience burnout at work, exceeding rates in other countries like Singapore and Indonesia (Desiderio, 2022). Surprisingly, Filipino healthcare workers have a job satisfaction rate of 69%, a vital factor in retaining talent in the face of a severe shortage of medical professionals in the Philippines (Desiderio, 2022). This shortage is exacerbated by the urgent need to fill thousands of vacant healthcare positions, leading to a "brain drain" as qualified nurses pursue better-paying opportunities overseas (Beltran, 2023). The struggle continues, with thousands of aspiring nurses failing board exams in recent years while Filipino nurses remain among the lowest-paid healthcare professionals in Southeast Asia (Beltran, 2023).

Within the context of the Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC), healthcare employees are essential for providing critical services to every patient. R2TMC recognizes the importance of fostering a positive work environment to reduce burnout, enhance employee satisfaction, and ultimately improve commitment, retention, and the quality of patient care.

However, a significant issue arose during the implementation of the Safety Walkaround in October 2023 at R2TMC, revealing a disturbingly low nurse-to-patient ratio well below the recommended standard. With only 5-6 nurses per ward responsible for over 100 patients, this inadequate ratio, as highlighted in the R2TMC Patient Safety Report (2023), could contribute to employee burnout and compromise patient care quality.

R2TMC's staffing challenges mirror the national healthcare worker shortages, evidenced by a notably high turnover rate, especially among temporary medical personnel and nursing staff. This concerning trend, marked by substantial increases in resignations, transfers,

and leave of absence applications, underscores the urgent need for strategic interventions to address burnout and enhance job satisfaction among healthcare workers at R2TMC.

In light of these challenges, there is a notable gap in the existing literature regarding the specific impact of organizational climate and commitment on healthcare professionals' well-being, job burnout, and job satisfaction. While individual studies have explored these factors independently, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding of how they interact, particularly in the context of healthcare workers in the Philippines, such as those at R2TMC.

To address this gap, a study was conducted to investigate the complex relationships between employee profiles, organizational climate, organizational commitment, job burnout, and job satisfaction among healthcare workers at R2TMC. The research aimed to shed light on the factors influencing healthcare professionals in their workplace, with a particular emphasis on the interplay between organizational dynamics and individual experiences. By developing a model to mitigate burnout and enhance satisfaction, this study sought to offer valuable insights that could guide healthcare organizations globally in improving employee well-being and job satisfaction in the demanding healthcare sector.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the predictors of job burnout and job satisfaction among the healthcare workforce at Region II Trauma and Medical Center and develop a model to alleviate job burnout and enhance job satisfaction. Specifically, the study answered the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of personal and professional?
2. What is the level of perceptions of the respondents on the organizational climate of R2TMC, in terms of affective, continuance, and normative?
3. What is the level of perceptions of the respondents on the organizational climate of R2TMC, in terms of clarity, standards, individual responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment?
4. What is the level of job burnout of the respondents when measured in terms of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment?
5. What is the level of job satisfaction of the respondents when measured in terms of salary, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, co-workers, nature of work and communication?
6. Is there a significant relationship between organizational climate, organizational commitment, profile and job burnout to job satisfaction?
7. Is there a significant relationship between organizational climate, organizational commitment, profile and job satisfaction to job burnout?

Methodology

The research methodology employed in this study at Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC) involved a descriptive-inferential approach with a systematic collection and analysis of numerical data to understand and explain phenomena. The study included a structured survey to gather quantitative data on employee profiles, organizational climate, organizational commitment, job burnout, and job satisfaction. Statistical analyses, such as regression, were utilized to explore relationships and predict outcomes based on independent variables.

The survey questionnaires were complemented by Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) to provide deeper insights into employees' perceptions and experiences. The triangulation of results from both methods ensured a robust interpretation of the data. The research environment at R2TMC, which has a rich history and significant role in healthcare in Nueva Vizcaya, served as the backdrop for exploring organizational climate, commitment, burnout, and satisfaction among healthcare workers.

The study population included a diverse workforce at R2TMC, with regular employees and Contract of Service personnel, totaling 1,446 individuals. A mix of stratified and systematic random sampling procedures ensured comprehensive representation across different services within the hospital and enhanced the validity of the findings.

The research instrument comprised a structured survey questionnaire divided into five parts: Socio-demographic Profiles, Organizational Climate, Organizational Commitment, Job Burnout, and Job Satisfaction. Well-validated scales were used to measure organizational commitment, burnout, and satisfaction, allowing for a nuanced analysis of the data collected. The survey instruments underwent expert validation and reliability testing to ensure accuracy and consistency of the results.

The data collection procedure followed ethical guidelines, including obtaining permission from the appropriate authorities and obtaining informed consent from participants. The survey questionnaires were administered using a paper-and-pencil format in English or Tagalog, catering to participant preferences. Data analysis involved calculating means, standard deviations, ANOVA, and multiple regression to draw conclusions and identify relationships between variables.

Ultimately, the study aimed to develop a model for reducing job burnout and enhancing job satisfaction among healthcare workers at R2TMC. By employing a rigorous research methodology, including diverse data collection methods and robust statistical analyses, the

study sought to provide valuable insights that could drive improvements in employee well-being and organizational climate within the healthcare setting.

Results and Discussion

Profile of R2TMC Employees

This section provides an analysis of the socio-demographic profile of R2TMC employees, covering their personal and professional attributes. These include age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, job position levels, years in the organization, service areas, appointment status, and work schedules, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. *Demographic profile of the respondents*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Age	23 - 30	109	34.7
	31 - 40	146	46.5
	41 - 50	36	11.5
	above 50	23	7.3
Gender	LGBTQ++	12	3.8
	Male	117	37.3
	Female	185	58.9
Civil Status	Widow	4	1.3
	Living-in	8	2.5
	Single	123	39.2
	Married	179	57.0
Highest Educational Attainment	Elementary	2	0.6
	High School	8	2.5
	College	255	81.2
	Post Graduate	49	15.6
Level of Position	SG 1 – 9 (1st Level)	113	36.0
	SG 10 – 24 (2nd Level)	199	63.4
	above SG 24	2	0.6
Years employed in R2TMC	1 - 5	175	55.7
	6 - 10	90	28.7
	11 - 15	25	8.0
	16 - 20	10	3.2
	21 - 25	6	1.9
	more than 25	8	2.5
Service	Finance	18	5.7
	Allied Health	28	8.9
	Hospital Operations and Medical	35	11.1
	Nursing	116	36.9
Status of Appointment	Contract of Service	117	37.3
	Permanent	38	12.1
		276	87.9
Work Schedule	24 hours	25	8.0
	Shifting	143	45.5
	Daily	146	46.5

Personal Profile

Age. The largest group of respondents falls within the 31-40 age bracket (46.5%), followed by the 23-30 age bracket (34.7%). Those aged 41-50 represent 11.5%, and those aged above 50 constitute 7.3%. This indicates a predominantly young workforce at R2TMC due to recent expansions, which suggests a potential need for further training and experience.

Gender. Most respondents are female (58.9%), with males representing 37.3%, and 3.8% identifying as LGBTQ++. This aligns with the gender distribution observed by R2TMC's Human Resources Management Office and indicates an inclusive work environment.

Civil Status. A majority of employees are married (57%), followed by single (39.2%), with a smaller fraction in common-law marriages (2.5%) or widowed (1.3%). The civil status distribution correlates with age demographics, typical in government institutions.

Highest Educational Attainment. Most respondents are college graduates (81.2%), with some holding postgraduate degrees (15.6%). High school graduates make up 2.5%, and elementary graduates 0.6%. Higher-level positions often require advanced degrees, explaining the education distribution.

Professional Profile

Level of Position. A majority occupy 2nd level positions with salary grades SG 10- 24 (63.4%), while 36% are in 1st level positions

(SG 1-9). Only 0.6% hold positions above SG 24, usually administrative roles. Second-level positions require professional civil service eligibility, while first-level roles typically require sub-professional eligibility or technical certificates.

Years Employed in R2TMC. Most employees have been with the institution for five years or less (55.7%), indicating significant recent hiring due to R2TMC's expansion. Those with 6-10 years of service represent 28.7%, with fewer employees having served more than ten years.

Service Areas. Employees are mostly engaged in nursing (37.3%) and medical services (36.9%), reflecting R2TMC's primary focus. Other areas include HOPSS (11.1%), Allied Health (8.9%), and finance (5.7%).

Status of Appointment. Most respondents have permanent positions (87.9%), while 12.1% are on contracts of service. This proportion illustrates the need for temporary staff due to the availability of permanent positions.

Work Schedule. Work schedules vary, with 46.5% on regular eight-hour shifts, 45.5% on rotating shifts for 24/7 coverage, and 8% on straight 24-hour shifts. Regular hours are typical for administrative/finance roles, whereas technical functions require varied schedules, especially during emergencies.

The detailed demographic data presented in this chapter offers crucial insights into the workforce composition at R2TMC, highlighting areas such as the predominance of a youthful, well-educated, and predominantly female workforce, along with significant variations in professional roles and tenure within the organization. This information sets the stage for understanding job satisfaction, burnout, and related factors in subsequent analyses.

Level of Perceived Organizational Climate at R2TMC

Organizational climate at R2TMC refers to the prevailing atmosphere, culture, and environment within the organization, influenced by factors such as policies, practices, values, and employee interactions. This climate plays a significant role in shaping employee attitudes, behaviors, satisfaction, and overall performance. The study measured various dimensions of organizational climate using a five-point scale, presenting the results in Table 2.

Table 2. *Level of perceptions in terms of organizational climate*

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>
Clarity	3.84	0.87	Very Satisfactory
Standards	3.78	0.83	Very Satisfactory
Responsibility	3.80	0.86	Very Satisfactory
Flexibility	3.63	0.88	Very Satisfactory
Rewards and Recognition	3.47	0.94	Very Satisfactory
Team Commitment	3.59	0.88	Very Satisfactory
Overall Organizational Climate	3.68	0.89	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4.20-5.00 = Excellent; 3.40-4.19 = Very Satisfactory; 2.60-3.39 = Satisfactory; 1.80-2.59 = Unsatisfactory; 1.00-1.79 = Poor

Clarity involves how well employees understand the organization's purpose, direction, and their roles in achieving its goals. The overall mean score for clarity is 3.84, indicating a "Very Satisfactory" level. The highest rating (4.23) is for the clarity in communicating the organization's overall direction and goals. This suggests that employees largely comprehend the mission, although there is room for improvement in involving them in strategic discussions and understanding management decisions that impact their well-being. This aligns with the thoughts of Seyyedmoharrami et al. (2019), who found that organizational clarity positively influences employee commitment and engagement.

Standards refer to the criteria used to assess the work environment and employee perceptions. The overall mean score here is 3.78, also rated as "Very Satisfactory." Employees are given clear, achievable objectives and adhere to standardized procedures and quality standards. This fosters accountability and continuous improvement, although slight variations in mentoring practices indicate areas for harmonization. The findings echo the research of Thompson et al. (2022), which suggests that adherence to standards in organizational settings is crucial for maintaining quality and consistency even though flexibility is also necessary.

Responsibility covers the delegation of authority, autonomy, and accountability within the organization. With an overall mean score of 3.80, "Very Satisfactory," employees are mostly held accountable for their performance (mean score of 4.07) and encouraged to work as a team (mean score of 4.03). There is a strong emphasis on training and team collaboration, but further minimizing managerial interventions could enhance autonomy. These findings align with Mishra and Tikoria's (2021) study, which highlights the importance of individual responsibility and the positive impacts of employee empowerment on organizational outcomes.

Flexibility reflects the organization's ability to adapt its practices, policies, and structures to changing circumstances and employee needs. The overall mean score is 3.63, rated as "Very Satisfactory." There is strong encouragement for creativity and independent thinking (mean score of 3.80), and work processes are streamlined (mean score of 3.66). Despite this, enhancing top management's acceptance of diverse viewpoints (mean score of 3.46) could further improve flexibility. Similar findings by Maglalang et al. (2021) suggest that workplace flexibility positively impacts employee well-being and job satisfaction by providing a supportive environment that accommodates individual needs.

Rewards and Recognition denote the practices for acknowledging and rewarding employee contributions and achievements. The overall mean score is 3.47, "Very Satisfactory." Detailed performance standards are well communicated (mean score of 3.78) and non-monetary rewards and positive feedback are appreciated (mean scores of 3.50 and 3.49). Improvements are needed in providing timely, performance-based rewards (mean score of 3.39) and promotion opportunities (mean score of 3.24). This aspect of organizational climate is critical, as highlighted by Bingham et al. (2022), who emphasize that comprehensive total reward management systems are essential for enhancing employee motivation and retention in medical workplaces.

Team Commitment encompasses the degree to which team members are committed to their goals, values, and success. The overall mean score for team commitment is 3.59, rated as "Very Satisfactory." Indicators such as cooperation among employees (mean score of 3.74) and valuing diversity (mean score of 3.71) stood out. There is a strong commitment to teamwork and diversity, but opportunities exist in enhancing social interactions through team-building activities and ensuring collaborative decision-making processes. Chacón-Moscoso et al. (2023) similarly found that fostering a cohesive and collaborative team environment is essential for realizing organizational goals and improving performance.

The overall organizational climate at R2TMC, represented by an average mean value of 3.68 and a standard deviation of 0.89, is described as "Very Satisfactory." This positive climate, shaped by clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards, and team commitment, creates a conducive environment for employee growth and is integral to achieving the healthcare institution's goals. These findings highlight areas where R2TMC excels and where there is potential for further improvement to enhance employee satisfaction, reduce burnout, and boost organizational performance. The study underscores the importance of a well-rounded organizational climate, which is crucial for employee well-being, commitment, and overall institutional success.

Level of Perceived Organizational Commitment among Healthcare Workforce

Organizational commitment refers to an employee's psychological attachment to their organization, encompassing the extent to which they identify with the organization's goals and values, feel a sense of belonging, and are willing to exert effort on behalf of the organization. The study measured organizational commitment at R2TMC using a four-point Likert scale, presenting results for various dimensions of commitment in Table 3.

Table 3. *Level of organizational commitment of R2TMC personnel*

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>
Affective Commitment	2.97	0.74	High
Continuance Commitment Scale	2.64	0.81	High
Normative Commitment	2.95	0.78	High
Overall Job Commitment	2.85	0.79	High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 = Very High; 2.51-3.25 = High; 1.76-2.49 = Low; 1.00-1.75 = Very Low

Affective Commitment describes an employee's emotional attachment to the organization. Employees with high affective commitment feel a sense of belonging, loyalty, and pride in their organization. The study found a predominantly high level of emotional attachment and identification with R2TMC, indicated by a mean score of 2.97. Employees expressed a strong desire to spend their careers at R2TMC and identified closely with the organization's challenges and problems. These findings suggest stability and continuity in the workforce, which is beneficial for organizational culture and long-term success. Woznyj (2019) supports these findings, stating that creating a positive climate fosters positive job attitudes, such as high organizational commitment, which further enhances employee engagement and retention.

Continuance Commitment refers to the perceived cost of leaving the organization. Employees with high continuance commitment stay because they feel they have invested too much to leave or believe they have limited alternative employment options. The study's findings indicate a high level of continuance commitment among R2TMC employees, with a mean score of 2.64. Respondents expressed that staying at R2TMC was a matter of necessity as much as desire, fearing that their lives would be significantly disrupted if they left. However, this high level of continuance commitment can signify a potential risk for the organization, as it may indicate that employees are less engaged and motivated. Deressa et al. (2022) highlighted a similar concern, noting that low organizational commitment among healthcare professionals could result from inadequate support and growth opportunities. R2TMC should, therefore, focus on enhancing intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction to counterbalance high continuance commitment.

Normative Commitment is based on an employee's sense of obligation to stay with the organization due to loyalty or reciprocity for the organization's investment in their development. The study revealed high normative commitment among R2TMC employees, with a mean score of 2.95. Employees felt morally and ethically bound to remain with R2TMC, believing that the organization deserved their loyalty. This high normative commitment can be a valuable asset as it indicates strong dedication and conscientiousness. However, it is important that this commitment is not solely based on feelings of obligation; employees should also feel valued and supported in their roles. Du et al. (2019) noted that investment in employee development and a supportive work environment are crucial for sustaining high normative commitment. R2TMC should, therefore, ensure that they continuously address employees' needs and expectations to maintain this level of commitment.

The overall level of organizational commitment at R2TMC, reflected by a mean value of 2.85, is qualitatively interpreted as "high."

This strong commitment indicates that employees feel a significant sense of obligation to remain with the organization. During interviews, many respondents shared that they felt a deep sense of purpose, fulfillment, and obligation to R2TMC, attributing their commitment to the meaningful work and supportive colleagues. However, records from the Human Resource Management department showing high turnover rates suggest that this sense of commitment may be influenced by tenure and current economic conditions. Continuous improvement in areas such as training opportunities and career advancement could further solidify organizational commitment. This level of commitment is essential for fostering a loyal and dedicated workforce, which in turn, contributes to the overall success and effectiveness of the organization.

Level of Job Burnout Among Healthcare Workers

Job burnout represents a significant and recurring issue in government-run health institutions, defined in this study as the state of emotional, physical, and mental exhaustion caused by prolonged exposure to chronic work-related stress. Job burnout can greatly diminish productivity and often leads to personnel turnover. The study at R2TMC measured burnout using various criteria and scales, focusing on emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment as illustrated in Table 4, 5, and 6.

Table 4. *Frequency and percent distribution of R2TMC personnel on the level of job burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion*

<i>Emotional Exhaustion</i>			
<i>Level of Burnout</i>			
	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Low	0 – 16	50	15.9
Moderate	17 – 26	129	41.0
High	27 – above	135	42.9
Total		314	100
Mean		24.04 (Moderate)	

Legend: 16 and below = Low; 17-26 = Moderate; 27 and above= High

Emotional Exhaustion was the first variable assessed, with findings indicating that 15.9% of the 314 respondents experienced low levels of burnout, 41.0% exhibited moderate burnout, and 42.9% had high levels of burnout. The mean score of 24.04 fell into the moderate category, suggesting that, on average, respondents faced considerable emotional exhaustion. Key informants reported feeling drained and emotionally spent, with indicators such as "working with people all day long requires a great deal of effort" scoring the highest (mean of 4.98). These findings emphasize the urgent need for interventions to mitigate the negative consequences of burnout. In line with these observations, Rathert (2022) suggests that a supportive work environment can provide psychological resources to buffer against burnout, fostering a culture of empathy and psychological safety.

Table 5. *Frequency and percent distribution of R2TMC personnel on the level of job burnout in terms of depersonalization*

<i>Level of Burnout</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Low	0 – 6	0	0
Moderate	7 – 12	99	32
High	13 - above	215	68
Total		314	100.0
Mean		17.10 (High)	

Legend: 6 and below = Low; 7-12 = Moderate; 13 and above= High

Depersonalization results revealed that 68% of R2TMC personnel experienced high levels of burnout, manifesting as feelings of cynicism, detachment, and negativity towards clients, with a mean score of 17.10. This level of depersonalization often leads to reduced empathy and compassion fatigue, negatively impacting patient care and overall organizational effectiveness. Notably, no respondents reported low levels of burnout. Research by Hamdan and Hamra (2017) supports these findings, indicating a positive association between burnout, job turnover intentions, and exposure to workplace violence. This underscores the need for comprehensive strategies to address work-related stressors and promote a supportive work environment.

Table 6. *Frequency and percent distribution of R2TMC personnel on the level of job burnout in terms of reduced personal accomplishment*

<i>Level of Burnout</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Low	39 – above	243	77
Moderate	32 – 38	47	15
High	0 – 31	24	8
Total		314	100.0
Mean		45.61 (Low)	

Legend: 39 and above= Low; 32-38 = Moderate; 31 and below = High

Reduced Personal Accomplishment was found to be lower than other burnout dimensions, with 77% of respondents reporting low levels of burnout in this area. The mean score of 45.61 suggests that most personnel perceive themselves as having a high level of personal accomplishment and a sense of achievement in their work. Indicators such as "I feel refreshed when I have been close to my colleagues or clients at work" (mean of 5.91) highlighted positive interactions and relationships at work. This aligns with findings by Maslach et al. (1996) and a study by Nwankwo, Obi, and Aboh (2013), which showed a positive relationship between self-efficacy and feelings of personal accomplishment.

Overall, the study revealed significant levels of job burnout among R2TMC personnel, particularly in emotional exhaustion and depersonalization. The high prevalence of burnout underscores the necessity for proactive interventions to address work-related stress, create a supportive work environment, and promote employee well-being. By fostering a culture of support, empathy, and psychological safety, R2TMC can mitigate the negative effects of burnout, ultimately enhancing employee engagement, satisfaction, and performance.

Level of job satisfaction among the healthcare workforce

Job satisfaction among healthcare workers is defined as the pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from one's job experiences, encompassing various facets such as pay, promotion, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, co-workers, nature of work, and communication. In assessing the job satisfaction levels among R2TMC personnel, it was found that the overall level of job satisfaction is high, with a mean score of 2.78 (SD=0.82), reflected in Table 7.

Findings from the study, as presented in Table 7, revealed mixed perceptions among R2TMC personnel regarding different aspects of job satisfaction. Employees reported high satisfaction levels with pay, promotion opportunities, supervision, and co-workers, while some areas like fringe benefits and operating conditions showed discrepancies and areas needing improvement.

Table 7. Level of job satisfaction of R2TMC personnel

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>
Pay	2.73	0.81	High
Promotion	2.60	0.80	High
Supervision	3.12	0.80	High
Fringe Benefits	2.61	0.84	High
Contingent Rewards	2.58	0.74	High
Operating Conditions	2.34	0.77	Low
Co-workers	2.99	0.76	High
Nature of Work	3.20	0.68	High
Communication	2.84	0.77	High
Overall Job Satisfaction	2.78	0.82	High

Legend: 3.25-4.00 = Very High; 2.50-3.24 = High; 1.75-2.49 = Low; 1.00-1.74 = Very Low

Understanding the significance of pay in influencing employee morale and job satisfaction, the study highlighted the need for transparent processes for salary adjustments and raises to align with employee expectations. Previous literature by Elarabi and Johari (2015) supported the association between pay, compensation, and employee job satisfaction. Additionally, insights from Nemmaniwar and Deshpande (2016) stressed the importance of transparent communication in pay decisions to ensure employee appreciation and value.

Promotion opportunities emerged as a crucial factor impacting morale, motivation, and career progression among employees at R2TMC. Addressing perceptions of advancement opportunities and implementing transparent promotion processes were suggested strategies in enhancing employee satisfaction, as noted by Singh Rajkumar (2015). Effective communication and support for skill development were also highlighted as key elements in facilitating career progression and bolstering job satisfaction.

Supervision played a vital role in job satisfaction levels, with competent and fair supervisors contributing to a positive work environment. Research by Risky et al. (2023) reinforced the positive correlation between effective supervision and increased job satisfaction. Management strategies to promote fairness and empathy among supervisors were emphasized to enhance organizational effectiveness and employee satisfaction.

Fringe benefits, though generally rated high, showed disparities in perceived adequacy, with some employees expressing dissatisfaction. Addressing these disparities and ensuring equitable benefits aligned with industry standards were suggested strategies to enhance overall satisfaction. Operating conditions, characterized by procedural red tape and excessive paperwork, required streamlining to improve the work environment and employee satisfaction.

Employee relationships with co-workers were attributed to a harmonious and supportive work environment, aligning with positive sentiments and high satisfaction levels reported. Effective communication practices among staff were crucial in fostering positive relationships and collaboration, subsequently enhancing overall satisfaction, as supported by existing literature.

The nature of work had a significant impact on job satisfaction, with employees expressing enjoyment and pride in their tasks, emphasizing the need for meaningful and fulfilling job experiences. Addressing occasional feelings of meaninglessness in work tasks

was crucial for maintaining morale and engagement, as noted by the study. Effective communication within R2TMC was generally rated positively, albeit with some employees feeling misinformed, pointing to the importance of clear and inclusive communication practices to foster a positive work environment and enhance job satisfaction.

Overall, the study reflected a high level of job satisfaction among R2TMC personnel, particularly in areas such as pay, promotion, supervision, and co-worker relationships. However, targeted interventions in areas like fringe benefits, operating conditions, and communication were recommended to further enhance employee satisfaction and organizational performance. Further research focusing on organizational climate and operational processes within R2TMC was suggested to address observed low levels of job satisfaction and ensure a positive work environment for employees.

Relationship Between Organizational Climate, Organizational Commitment, Profile and Job Satisfaction to Job Burnout

The study extensively explores the intricate relationship between organizational climate, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, profile and job burnout among healthcare personnel, with a particular focus on emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment as critical variables. The analysis uncovers significant predictors impacting job burnout across these dimensions, reflected in Table 8.

Table 8. Regression of Level of Job Burnout to Independent Variables

Job Burnout	Predictors	Beta	t - value	Significance
Emotional Exhaustion	Overall Job Satisfaction	-.517	-8.499	<.001
	Continuance commitment	.179	3.584	<.001
	Rewards and Recognition	.146	2.387	.018
Dependent Variable = Emotional Exhaustion; R value = 0.49; R Squared = 0.24; F value = 31.90; Significance = <0.001; Constant= 6.95				
Depersonalization	Overall Job Satisfaction	-.700	-9.070	.000
	Rewards and Recognition	.156	2.566	.011
	Working Hours	.125	2.506	.013
Dependent Variable = Depersonalization; R value = 0.52; R Squared = 0.27; F value = 32.61; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 6.21				
Reduced Personal Accomplishment	Pay	.461	8.966	.000
	Highest Educational Attainment	.146	3.168	.002
	Clarity	.157	3.106	.002
	Contingent Rewards	-.185	-3.546	.000
	Nature of Work	.175	3.230	.001
Dependent Variable = Personal Accomplishment; R value = 0.59; R Squared = 0.35; F value = 32.76; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 0.94				
Overall Job Burnout	Overall Job Satisfaction	-.615	-8.177	<.001
	Pay	.218	3.383	.001
	Overall Organizational Climate	.189	2.974	.003
	Normative Commitment	.123	2.138	.033
Dependent Variable = Job Burnout; R value = 0.43; R Squared = 0.18; F value = 17.26; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 5.45				

Job burnout is one of the ever present and recurring issues rooted in any government run health institution. It is defined as the state of emotional, physical, and mental exhaustion caused by prolonged exposure to chronic work-related stress and the diminishing productivity and personnel turnover. Identifying the factors causing of job burnout is one of the objectives of the study. The actors affecting the severity of each of the variables of job burnout were identified and presented in the study.

Emotional Exhaustion

Significant predictors included continuance commitment, rewards and recognition, and overall job satisfaction, with specific beta coefficients indicating their impact on burnout levels. Continuance commitment, as indicated by a positive beta coefficient, highlighted that personnel who felt invested in the organization or perceived limited alternative employment options were more prone to emotional exhaustion. The study suggested that despite experiencing emotional drain from work-related stress, individuals persisted due to perceived costs of leaving, leading to increased emotional exhaustion. To address this, administrators were advised to reduce exposure to chronic stress by promoting a supportive workplace environment.

On the other hand, the positive beta coefficient associated with rewards and recognition demonstrated that practices acknowledging and rewarding employee contributions could elevate emotional exhaustion levels. Employees striving for recognition may push themselves beyond regular hours, potentially resulting in exhaustion. Ensuring the implementation of appropriate recognition practices without compromising emotional well-being was recommended to alleviate emotional burnout.

Conversely, the negative beta coefficient linked to overall job satisfaction indicated that positive job experiences minimizing dissatisfaction were correlated with decreased emotional exhaustion. Unpleasant work experiences leading to discontentment were

associated with higher emotional burnout levels. Enhancing job satisfaction was thus highlighted as a crucial strategy to reduce emotional exhaustion among medical personnel.

The study's findings resonated with Li et al.'s research on Chinese hospital staff, emphasizing the significant impact of factors such as continuance commitment, rewards and recognition, and job satisfaction on emotional exhaustion and overall job burnout. Both studies underlined the importance of organizational factors in shaping burnout experiences, emphasizing the need for supportive work environments and effective strategies to address emotional exhaustion and promote employee well-being.

The research highlighted key predictors influencing emotional exhaustion among healthcare workers and provided valuable insights for mitigating job burnout and fostering employee well-being in healthcare settings, drawing attention to the importance of organizational support and recognition practices.

Depersonalization

Significant predictors identified included rewards and recognition as well as working hours, with an emphasis on the impact of overall job satisfaction. The analysis indicated a substantial relationship between these predictors and job burnout in terms of depersonalization, with them accounting for a significant portion of the variability in the dependent variable. Specifically, the positive beta coefficient associated with rewards and recognition highlighted how acknowledging and appreciating employee contributions can lead to increased job burnout in terms of depersonalization. Similarly, the relationship between working hours and depersonalization indicated that extended work hours could contribute to higher levels of burnout, particularly in dealing with challenging clients.

Conversely, the negative beta coefficient linked to overall job satisfaction underlined how positive job experiences can mitigate depersonalization-related burnout, emphasizing the importance of enhancing job satisfaction to reduce negative outcomes.

The study's findings shared similarities with Nitafan's research in 2020 on job burnout among local government employees, emphasizing the significance of predictors such as rewards and recognition, working hours, and overall job satisfaction in influencing burnout among personnel. Both studies underscored the importance of addressing these predictors to mitigate job burnout and promote well-being among employees through organizational interventions and enhanced job satisfaction measures.

The research conducted at R2TMC, along with Nitafan's study, aimed to understand and address job burnout through empirical research and evidence-based interventions, despite differences in organizational contexts and specific predictors examined. This shared goal highlights the importance of implementing proactive measures to alleviate burnout and enhance the well-being of personnel in various institutional settings.

Reduced Personal Accomplishment

The analysis revealed significant predictors including pay, highest educational attainment, clarity, nature of work, and contingent rewards. These variables were found to impact the level of job burnout in terms of personal accomplishment, with a substantial relationship identified.

Higher compensation (pay) in the medical personnel's role was associated with a higher level of reduced personal accomplishment, indicating a complex relationship between financial rewards and job satisfaction. Similarly, individuals with higher educational attainment tended to have a stronger belief in personal accomplishment due to their specialized tasks or management responsibilities critical to the institution's efficient operation. Clarity regarding the organization's purpose and direction was found to positively impact personal accomplishment, highlighting the importance of a positive organizational climate in enhancing employee engagement and satisfaction. Moreover, the nature of work, especially tasks involving specialized technical skills or critical responsibilities, was linked to a higher sense of personal accomplishment among medical personnel.

Contrastingly, contingent rewards tied to specific performance goals showed a negative association with personal accomplishment. While such rewards could motivate individuals, failure to meet performance standards could lead to feelings of inadequacy and worthlessness, contributing to job burnout.

The study's findings align closely with similar research on reduced personal accomplishment among healthcare personnel conducted by Ogundipe et al. (2014). Both studies emphasize the nuanced relationship between pay, education, organizational clarity, and contingent rewards in influencing personal accomplishment and job satisfaction among healthcare professionals.

The results underscore the importance of considering diverse factors that impact personal accomplishment and job burnout, emphasizing the need for a balanced approach to recognition and reward systems within healthcare institutions. Transparent communication, professional development, and a supportive organizational environment play crucial roles in fostering a sense of fulfillment and reducing job burnout among personnel.

Overall Level of Job Burnout

Table 8 illustrates that of the various independent variables used in the study, four (4) exhibited significant relationships with the overall level of job burnout among R2TMC personnel. The multiple regression analysis shows an F-computed value of 17.26, and the analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the multiple regression denotes a probability of <0.001, exceeding the 0.01 level of probability. The result

indicates a highly significant relationship between the identified predictors and the overall level of job burnout among R2TMC personnel. The regression coefficient $R = 0.43$ denotes a substantial relationship between the identified predictors and the dependent variable. However, the coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.18$ indicates that the identified predictors account for 18% of the variability of the dependent variable.

Of the identified significant predictors, three exhibited positive beta coefficients, which include pay, overall organizational climate, and normative commitment, whereas the variable overall job satisfaction displayed a negative beta coefficient. The positive beta coefficient between the variable pay and the overall level of job burnout among R2TMC personnel reveals that medical personnel with higher compensation for specific job responsibilities tend to have a higher level of personal accomplishment, which can lead to increased job burnout. Those with higher pay often undertake critical functions beyond their normal schedules, contributing to increased stress and ultimately, more significant job burnout, especially when compared to lower-paid personnel engaged in manual labor tasks.

Another variable showing a positive relationship with the dependent variable is overall organizational climate. The positive beta coefficient between the two variables implies that the prevailing atmosphere within an organization significantly influences employee attitudes and behaviors. Stringent implementation of organizational policies and practices urging employees to take on more work may lead to increased stress and build up to severe job burnout.

The last variable exhibiting a positive relationship with the dependent variable is normative commitment. The result suggests that employees driven by a sense of obligation to remain with the organization may sacrifice their professional development and well-being, leading to increased job burnout.

Conversely, the negative beta coefficient between the level of job burnout and overall job satisfaction indicates that personnel experiencing positive job experiences may exhibit lower levels of job burnout. Strategies to improve job satisfaction should be developed by the administration to minimize job burnout within the medical institution.

The study derived the following prediction equation:

$$Y = 5.45 - 0.615x_1 + 0.218x_2 + 0.189x_3 + 0.123x_4$$

The equation can predict up to 18% of the variability in the job burnout of R2TMC personnel. Of the identified significant predictors, overall job satisfaction, pay, and organizational climate had the most substantial effects. Therefore, interventions aimed at improving job burnout among R2TMC personnel should prioritize these variables. However, since the identified predictors collectively account for only up to 18% of the variability of the dependent variable, caution should be exercised when using the derived equation for predicting overall job burnout.

Connections to reviewed studies like Jiang et al. (2019) and Kokkinos (2018) unveil similarities and differences, emphasizing the importance of psychological resources and organizational factors in mitigating burnout across various professions and sectors.

In conclusion, the findings from the present study, combined with research by Jiang et al. (2019) and Kokkinos (2018), underscore the multifaceted nature of burnout and highlight the critical role of organizational factors in understanding and addressing burnout. Understanding the interplay between individual characteristics, organizational climate, and psychological resources is vital for developing effective interventions to mitigate burnout and promote employee well-being across different professions and sectors.

Relationship Between Organizational Climate, Organizational Commitment, Profile and Job Burnout to Job Satisfaction

One of the hypotheses tested in the study is whether a significant relationship exists between the variable's organizational climate, organizational commitment, profile and job burnout to job satisfaction. In testing the hypothesis, the multiple regression and correlation analysis was explored. Each of the variables encompassing job satisfaction and the overall level of job satisfaction were tested as to their relationships and significant predictors were identified per variable. The result of the regression analysis is presented per table and discussed extensively per variable.

Table 9. Regression of Level of Job Satisfaction to Independent Variables

Job Satisfaction	Predictors	Beta	t - value	Significance
Pay/Salary	Reduced Personal Accomplishment	.525	10.466	<.001
	Overall Job Burnout Level	-.197	-4.108	<.001
	Status of Appointment	.137	2.962	.003
	Overall Organizational Commitment	.208	4.398	<.001
	Educational Attainment	-.105	-2.246	.025
Dependent Variable = Pay; R value = 0.606; R Squared = 0.367; F value = 35.698; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 1.427				
Promotion	Rewards and Recognition	.310	5.482	<.001
	Overall Organizational Commitment	.178	3.191	.002
	Emotional Exhaustion	-.134	-2.660	.008
	Status of Appointment	.119	2.366	.019
Dependent Variable = Promotion; R value = 0.48; R Squared = 0.23; F value = 23.25; Significance = <0.001; Constant= 1.20				

Supervision	Rewards and Recognition	.310	4.319	<.001
	Depersonalization	-.233	-4.851	<.001
	Standards	.153	2.115	.035
	Service	.101	2.101	.036
	Civil Status	-.138	-2.795	.006
	Age	.100	1.972	.050
Dependent Variable = Supervision; R value = 0.57; R Squared = 0.32; F value = 24.13; Significance = <0.001; Constant= 2.12				
Fringe Benefits	Rewards and Recognition	.311	5.212	.000
	Affective Commitment	.192	3.157	.002
	Civil Status	-.129	-2.609	.010
	Emotional Exhaustion	-.129	-2.523	.012
Dependent Variable = Fringe Benefits; R value = 0.50; R Squared = 0.25; F value = 25.66; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 2.27				
Contingent Rewards	Affective Commitment	.264	4.440	<.001
	Overall Job Burnout	-.261	-5.313	<.001
	Flexibility	.214	3.653	<.001
Dependent Variable = Contingent Rewards; R value = 0.53; R Squared = 0.28; F value = 39.85; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 1.91				
Operating Conditions	Overall Job Burnout	-.271	-5.092	.000
	Rewards and Recognition	.437	3.483	.001
	Overall Organizational Climate	-.281	-2.246	.025
Dependent Variable = Operating Conditions; R value = 0.36; R Squared = 0.13; F value = 15.10; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 2.78				
Co-Workers	Affective Commitment	.353	6.914	.000
	Emotional Exhaustion	-.291	-6.009	.000
	Reduced Personal Accomplishment	.139	2.797	.005
Dependent Variable = Co-Workers; R value = 0.58; R Squared = 0.34; F value = 31.39; Significance = <0.001; Constant= 2.01				
Nature of Work	Affective Commitment	.442	6.373	.000
	Depersonalization	-.246	-5.481	.000
	Gender	-.203	-4.627	.000
	Reduced Personal Accomplishment	.143	3.134	.002
	Normative commitment	.353	3.904	.000
	Overall Organizational Commitment	-.354	-3.188	.002
Dependent Variable = Nature of Work; R value = 0.67; R Squared = 0.44; F value = 41.56; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 2.33				
Communication	Affective Commitment	.293	5.676	.000
	Clarity	.284	4.457	.000
	Depersonalization	-.186	-4.549	.000
	Gender	-.151	-3.797	.000
	Rewards and Recognition	.218	3.348	.001
	Reduced Personal Accomplishment	.101	2.462	.014
Dependent Variable = Communication; R value = 0.74; R Squared = 0.55; F value = 46.78; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 1.10				
Overall Job Satisfaction	Affective Commitment	.247	4.847	<0.001
	Emotional Exhaustion	-.208	-4.307	<0.001
	Rewards and Recognition	.308	7.162	<0.001
	Reduced Personal Accomplishment	.113	2.989	.003
	Depersonalization	-.142	-2.870	.004
	Gender	-.103	-2.807	.005
	Normative commitment	.118	2.792	.006
	Service	.093	2.588	.010
Dependent Variable = Overall Job Satisfaction; R value = 0.786; R Squared = 0.618; F value = 61.647; Significance = <0.001; Constant = 1.847				

Using multiple regression analysis, the study identified key findings on how independent variables affect job satisfaction in terms of pay/salary, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, nature of work, co-workers, and communication.

Pay/Salary

Identified predictors with positive effects on job satisfaction in terms of pay/salary were reduced personal accomplishment, status of appointment, and overall organizational commitment. Factors such as overall job burnout level and educational attainment displayed negative effects on job satisfaction.

The results indicated a significant association between the variables studied and job satisfaction, with the identified predictors explaining 36.7% of the variability in pay satisfaction. Personnel experiencing lower levels of burnout were more satisfied with their salary, while those facing severe burnout felt their compensation did not match the stress of their job. The study emphasized that caution should be taken when predicting personnel satisfaction solely based on the identified predictors, as they accounted for only a portion of the variability in pay satisfaction.

Furthermore, the findings of Yantib and Untaric (2020) align closely with the study results, emphasizing the importance of providing adequate salary to administrators that aligns with the demands of their roles. Both studies highlighted key factors influencing job satisfaction related to pay, such as permanent appointments, high personal accomplishment, strong organizational commitment, low job burnout, and lower educational attainment.

Additionally, individuals with lower educational attainments were found to be more satisfied with their salaries, suggesting that realistic salary expectations and perceived qualifications influence satisfaction levels. The correlation between lower burnout and higher salary satisfaction underscored the significance of justifying compensation relative to job stress, indicating the need to address job burnout to enhance satisfaction with salary.

Promotion

Positive effects on job satisfaction in terms of promotion were observed from rewards and recognition, overall organizational commitment, and status of appointment. Conversely, emotional exhaustion (a component of job burnout) was linked to negative effects on promotion satisfaction.

The identified predictors collectively explained 23% of the variability in satisfaction with promotion for personnel. Individuals who received rewards and recognition, demonstrated high organizational commitment, held permanent positions, and experienced lower emotional exhaustion tended to report higher satisfaction levels with regard to promotion processes. On the contrary, personnel lacking recognition, with low commitment levels, and suffering from emotional exhaustion due to chronic work-related stress, reported lower job satisfaction regarding promotion opportunities. Caution was advised in relying solely on the identified predictors for comprehensive predictions of job satisfaction related to promotion, as they only accounted for a portion of the variability.

Moreover, the findings correlated with a study conducted by Abou Hashish (2017) exploring factors influencing organizational climate and commitment in healthcare settings. The results highlighted the impact of promotion, rewards, organizational commitment, appointment status, and job burnout, particularly emotional exhaustion, on satisfaction levels among employees. Consistent with the current study, the importance of recognizing and rewarding employee efforts, enhancing organizational commitment and loyalty, and tackling job burnout were emphasized to improve job satisfaction, especially concerning promotional aspects. The alignment of results with the earlier research by Abou Hashish (2017) underscores the significance of these factors in shaping personnel's satisfaction levels and promoting a positive work environment.

Supervision

Six (6) variables were identified as significantly related to the levels of satisfaction with supervision for R2TMC personnel. The identified predictors collectively explained 32% of the variability in satisfaction with supervision. Positive effects on job satisfaction regarding supervision were observed from rewards and recognition, standards, service, and age.

Conversely, job burnout, specifically depersonalization, and civil status, had negative effects. Acknowledging and rewarding employee contributions, adhering to organizational values, having well-established standards, providing specialized services, and possessing experience were found to enhance job satisfaction with supervision. The negative correlation between job burnout, depersonalization, and satisfaction with supervision highlights the importance of maintaining a humane and empathetic workplace culture to promote job satisfaction.

Santana and Rico's study provided additional insights into the impact of various factors on job satisfaction, particularly concerning supervision, organizational commitment, and job burnout. Their findings reiterated the importance of recognition, clear standards, supportive services, experience, interpersonal dynamics, and personal circumstances in fostering satisfaction with supervision.

These findings offer valuable guidance for hospital administrators aiming to create a positive work environment, enhance employee satisfaction, and improve organizational performance based on acknowledgment, support, and understanding of personnel's needs and experiences.

Fringe Benefits

Four (4) variables were identified as significantly related to levels of satisfaction with fringe benefits for R2TMC personnel. The identified predictors collectively explained 25% of the variability in satisfaction with fringe benefits. Positive effects on job satisfaction concerning fringe benefits were observed from rewards and recognition, as well as affective commitment, while civil status and emotional exhaustion had negative effects. Acknowledging and rewarding employee contributions, fostering emotional attachment to the organization, and reducing emotional exhaustion were found to enhance job satisfaction with fringe benefits. The findings were aligned with a study conducted by Zanabazar and Jigjiddorj (2022) on fringe benefits, organizational climate, commitment, and job

burnout, emphasizing similar results regarding the significant effects of rewards and recognition, affective commitment, civil status, and emotional exhaustion on job satisfaction among R2TMC personnel.

The positive relationships between rewards and recognition, affective commitment, and job satisfaction, as well as the negative impact of civil status and emotional exhaustion, highlight the importance of recognizing employee contributions, fostering emotional connection to the organization, and managing emotional well-being to enhance satisfaction with fringe benefits. These findings underscore the value of organizational recognition, emotional attachment, and addressing emotional exhaustion in promoting satisfaction with benefits that contribute to overall well-being among hospital personnel.

Contingent Rewards

Three (3) variables—*affective commitment, flexibility, and overall job burnout*—were identified as significantly related to levels of satisfaction with contingent rewards for R2TMC personnel. The identified predictors collectively explained 28% of the variability in satisfaction with contingent rewards. Positive effects on job satisfaction concerning contingent rewards were observed from *affective commitment and flexibility*, while overall job burnout had a negative impact. *Affective commitment*, representing emotional attachment to the organization, significantly influenced job satisfaction with contingent rewards. Higher levels of emotional attachment correlated with greater job satisfaction regarding contingent rewards. *Flexibility* within the health institution, signifying adaptability to changing circumstances and employee needs, was positively associated with higher job satisfaction with contingent rewards. Conversely, rigid environments that failed to adapt saw lower satisfaction levels. The negative relationship between overall job burnout and job satisfaction with contingent rewards indicated that high levels of emotional, physical, and mental exhaustion due to chronic work-related stress led to reduced satisfaction with contingent rewards.

The study findings are echoed in research by Abdulkareem et al. (2019), which supports the importance of contingent rewards, affective commitment, and job burnout in influencing job satisfaction. Both studies highlight the positive impact of emotional attachment to the organization on job satisfaction, especially when contingent rewards are perceived as fair and motivating. Abdulkareem et al. (2019) noted the role of recognizing and rewarding employees' efforts in strengthening organizational commitment and overall job satisfaction.

While flexibility was not explicitly addressed in the study by Abdulkareem et al. (2019), the principle aligns with the idea that adaptable reward systems can meet employee needs and enhance satisfaction and commitment. Flexible organizational practices proved to support the effective implementation of contingent rewards, thereby boosting satisfaction and commitment levels.

In terms of job burnout, both studies underscore the negative correlation between burnout and job satisfaction concerning contingent rewards. High levels of burnout, resulting from prolonged work-related stress, were found to diminish the positive impact of contingent rewards on job satisfaction. Abdulkareem et al. (2019) also highlighted how appropriate rewards can help reduce burnout levels by alleviating stress, suggesting that a supportive reward system can mitigate exhaustion and enhance job satisfaction.

Operating Conditions

Three (3) variables - *rewards and recognition, overall job burnout, and organizational climate* - displayed significant relationships with job satisfaction in terms of operating conditions. The identified predictors collectively accounted for 13% of the variability in satisfaction with operating conditions. Positive effects on job satisfaction were observed from *rewards and recognition*, while overall job burnout and organizational climate had negative impacts. *Acknowledging and rewarding employee contributions* positively influenced job satisfaction with operating conditions. High levels of job burnout detrimentally affected job satisfaction, highlighting the need to address stress and exhaustion in the workplace. A negative organizational climate had an adverse impact on job satisfaction, underscoring the importance of fostering a conducive work environment for employee well-being.

The findings are similar to a study by Bustomi et al. (2021) that also investigated factors influencing job satisfaction in specific operational contexts. Both studies utilized multiple regression analysis to identify significant predictors of job satisfaction and highlighted the importance of specific variables in determining satisfaction levels. The positive relationship between *rewards and recognition* and job satisfaction underscores the significance of acknowledging and appreciating employee contributions in boosting satisfaction levels.

Additionally, the negative impacts of high job burnout and a negative organizational climate on job satisfaction align with both studies, emphasizing the need to address work-related stress and cultivate a supportive and positive work environment to enhance satisfaction levels among employees. Overall, the research underscores the critical role of effective recognition and reward systems, as well as the importance of mitigating job burnout and fostering a positive organizational culture, in improving job satisfaction among R2TMC personnel.

Co-workers

Three (3) variables - *affective commitment, reduced personal accomplishment, and emotional exhaustion* - demonstrated significant relationships with job satisfaction related to co-workers among R2TMC personnel. The identified predictors collectively explained 34% of the variability in satisfaction with co-workers. Positive effects on job satisfaction were observed from *affective commitment and reduced personal accomplishment*, while emotional exhaustion had a negative impact. *Affective commitment*, representing loyalty

and pride in the organization, significantly influenced satisfaction with co-workers, highlighting the importance of strong bonds and collective efforts in overcoming challenges within the organization. Personal accomplishment and a sense of fulfilment positively impacted job satisfaction with co-workers, emphasizing the significance of creating an environment that fosters employees' sense of achievement while addressing job burnout. Emotional exhaustion was found to diminish satisfaction levels, underscoring the need to mitigate work-related stress to enhance satisfaction with co-workers.

The findings correlated with a study by Ancarani et al. (2019), which also delved into understanding the dynamics between co-workers, organizational commitment, climate, and job burnout. Both studies highlighted the significant relationships between independent variables and job satisfaction concerning co-workers. The positive associations between affective commitment and reduced personal accomplishment with job satisfaction align with the notion that belongingness, loyalty, and personal fulfilment positively impact employees' perceptions of their co-workers, reflecting Ancarani et al.'s findings on organizational commitment.

Additionally, the negative impact of emotional exhaustion on job satisfaction resonates with both studies' examination of job burnout, suggesting that prolonged stress diminishes satisfaction with co-worker interactions. The research emphasizes the importance of cultivating positive organizational climates and addressing factors like job burnout to improve employee satisfaction, especially regarding relationships with co-workers. Interventions aimed at enhancing workplace environments and managing stressors could lead to improved satisfaction levels among employees and enhance organizational effectiveness.

Nature of Work

Six (6) variables - affective commitment, depersonalization, gender, reduced personal accomplishment, normative commitment, and overall organizational commitment - demonstrated significant relationships with job satisfaction concerning the nature of work for R2TMC personnel. The identified predictors collectively accounted for 44% of the variability in satisfaction with the nature of work. Positive effects on job satisfaction were observed from affective commitment, reduced personal accomplishment, and normative commitment, while depersonalization, gender, and overall organizational commitment had negative impacts. Affective commitment, signifying loyalty and pride in the organization, significantly influenced satisfaction levels with the nature of work, highlighting the importance of strong bonds and collective efforts in overcoming challenges within the organization. Personal accomplishment and a sense of achievement positively impacted job satisfaction, emphasizing the significance of fostering a work environment that enhances employees' sense of fulfilment while addressing job burnout. Normative commitment, stemming from loyalty and reciprocity tied to the organization's investment in employee development, was associated with higher satisfaction with the nature of work.

The findings correlated with a study by Gorgulu and Akilli (2017), emphasizing the significance of organizational commitment in shaping a positive work environment and boosting job satisfaction among healthcare workers. Both studies underscored the importance of developing a sense of belongingness, loyalty, and pride in the organization, as it influences employees' dedication and resilience in overcoming challenges. Administrators play a vital role in fostering an optimistic, confident, and cheerful work environment, as it enhances employees' sense of value and belonging, ultimately contributing to higher job satisfaction. Aligning work responsibilities with employees' loyalty and sense of belonging further reinforces this positive cycle by demonstrating recognition and reciprocation from the organization, fostering a mutually beneficial relationship. In conclusion, the study highlights how organizational commitment contributes to creating a supportive and rewarding workplace culture, enhancing job satisfaction for healthcare personnel. This understanding can guide administrators in implementing strategies to cultivate an environment that fosters loyalty, commitment, and positivity among employees, benefiting both individuals and the organization as a whole.

Communications

Eight (8) independent variables, including affective commitment, clarity, rewards and recognition, reduced personal accomplishment, service, depersonalization, gender, and individual responsibility, significantly influence job satisfaction in terms of communication. The identified predictors collectively explain 55% of the variability in satisfaction with communication. Positive effects on job satisfaction were observed from affective commitment, clarity, rewards and recognition, reduced personal accomplishment, and service, while depersonalization, gender, and individual responsibility had negative impacts. Affective commitment, clarity, and rewards and recognition were highlighted as key positive predictors of job satisfaction, emphasizing the positive impact of organizational loyalty, understanding roles, and recognition on communication satisfaction. The study also showed that creating a positive work environment, fostering a sense of achievement and recognition, and reducing negative attitudes can significantly improve job satisfaction regarding communication. The findings resonated with research by Seyyedmoharrami et al. (2019) regarding communication in hospital settings. Similarities included the emphasis on effective communication as a critical factor in enhancing job satisfaction among hospital staff. Both studies highlighted the importance of factors like affective commitment, clarity, and recognition in promoting satisfaction through effective communication.

The present study's identification of multiple predictors influencing communication satisfaction aligns with Seyyedmoharrami et al.'s (2019) research, reinforcing the significance of fostering a supportive and clear communicative environment, acknowledging contributions, and addressing negative interpersonal dynamics to improve overall job satisfaction among healthcare personnel. These findings underscore the value of targeted communication strategies in enhancing employee satisfaction and promoting a positive workplace culture in healthcare settings.

Overall Job Satisfaction

The significant predictors of overall job satisfaction among R2TMC personnel are listed in Table 8. This table illustrates that, of the various independent variables investigated in the study, eight exhibited significant relationships with the overall job satisfaction levels of R2TMC personnel. The multiple regression coefficient, $R = 0.786$, indicates a strong combined effect of these eight independent variables on the dependent variable. The adjusted coefficient of determination, $R^2 = 0.618$, suggests that 61.80% of the variability in the dependent variable can be explained by the combined effect of these eight independent variables.

Table 9 shows the regression of Overall Job Satisfaction on Independent Variables, identifying predictors such as Affective Commitment, Emotional Exhaustion, Rewards and Recognition, Reduced Personal Accomplishment, Depersonalization, Gender, Normative Commitment, and Service. It also lists their corresponding beta values, t-values, and significance levels.

Of the eight predictors identified, five demonstrated positive significant relationships with the dependent variable: Affective Commitment, Rewards and Recognition, Reduced Personal Accomplishment, Normative Commitment, and Service. Conversely, three independent variables—Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Gender—showed negative beta coefficients.

Affective Commitment stands out as a significant predictor of overall job satisfaction, indicated by a positive beta coefficient. This suggests that individuals with a higher level of commitment to their organization also report higher overall job satisfaction. Similarly, other predictors like Rewards and Recognition, Reduced Personal Accomplishment, Normative Commitment, and Service suggest higher job satisfaction levels for individuals receiving recognition, experiencing personal fulfillment, feeling obligated to the organization, and working in medical or nursing services.

However, negative beta coefficients in Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Gender indicate lower job satisfaction levels for individuals experiencing emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, as well as for those potentially belonging to the LGBTQ++ community.

The study's derived prediction equation offers insights into how these predictors impact the job satisfaction of R2TMC personnel. It underscores the significant effects of Affective Commitment, Emotional Exhaustion, and Rewards and Recognition on job satisfaction, suggesting their prioritization in interventions aimed at enhancing overall job satisfaction. The derived equation is:

$$Y = 1.847 + 0.247x_1 - 0.208x_2 + 0.308x_3 + 0.113x_4 - 0.142x_5 - 0.103x_6 + 0.118x_7 + 0.093x_8$$

Comparisons with studies such as Abdulkareem et al. (2019) reveal similarities, particularly in the positive relationships between Personal Accomplishment, Normative Commitment, and job satisfaction. However, discrepancies emerge regarding the connections between burnout, LGBTQ++ identity, and job satisfaction, suggesting the need for further research to understand these nuances across different populations and contexts.

Further exploration is necessary, particularly across diverse settings such as rural and urban areas, large and small organizations, and private and public sectors. This will help develop a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing job satisfaction across varied populations and contexts.

A related study by Gaunya (2016) also identifies several factors positively linked to job satisfaction. Both studies emphasize the significance of Affective Commitment in predicting job satisfaction, highlighting the importance of emotional attachment to the organization. Additionally, Rewards and Recognition play crucial roles in predicting job satisfaction in both studies, underscoring the value of feeling appreciated and valued by the organization. Normative Commitment is also highlighted as a predictor of job satisfaction, stressing the importance of a sense of obligation to the organization in fostering higher job satisfaction levels.

In summary, the findings of the present study, along with those of Abdulkareem et al. (2019) and Gaunya (2016), underscore the importance of Affective Commitment, Rewards and Recognition, Personal Accomplishment, and Normative Commitment in predicting job satisfaction. They emphasize the multifaceted nature of job satisfaction and the significance of organizational support, recognition, and personal fulfillment in creating positive work environments.

Model for Alleviating Job Burnout and Enhancing Job Satisfaction of Healthcare Workers at Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC)

Rationale

Job burnout and job satisfaction is a widely studied topic within organizational behavior and human resource management. Satisfied employees tend to be more productive and committed to their work, leading to lower turnover rates. The globalized healthcare sector has seen significant movement of employees seeking better opportunities, career growth, and overall job satisfaction. As a rapidly expanding, people-centric service sector, the healthcare industry must prioritize job satisfaction among hospital staff to retain talent and ensure effective healthcare delivery.

Job burnout negatively affects job satisfaction and can lead to job resignations, absenteeism, and reduced personal accomplishment. Reducing burnout and addressing basic workplace needs, such as adequate compensation and supportive work environments, are crucial for retaining healthcare workers. In the Philippines, burnout is common among healthcare professionals, leading to emotional

exhaustion. Strong correlations exist between job satisfaction, burnout, and turnover intention, indicating that both burnout and low job satisfaction significantly influence healthcare workers' intentions to leave their jobs.

Based on the study results, the researcher developed a model, illustrated in the figure below, that encompasses three key aspects: (1) the causes of job burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare workers, (2) the relationship between job burnout and job satisfaction, and (3) the interventions that can mitigate job burnout and enhance job satisfaction for healthcare personnel at R2TMC.

Model for Alleviating Job Burnout and Enhancing Job Satisfaction of Healthcare Workers at Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC)

To distinguish the different variables that affect job burnout and job satisfaction, the model uses color coding: fonts in blue are variables associated with job satisfaction; red are variables associated with job burnout; and green are variables associated with both job burnout and job satisfaction.

The identified factors that influence the level of burnout among healthcare workers include profile variables like pay, overall organizational climate, and organizational commitment in terms of normative commitment. These variables either mitigate or aggravate the level of burnout among health workers.

The identified factors that affect the level of job satisfaction among health personnel are profile variables such as gender and service; organizational climate in terms of rewards and recognition; and organizational commitment in terms of normative and affective commitment. The interaction of these variables affects the level of job satisfaction of health personnel in R2TMC. Arrows in the model illustrate these relationships.

Broken or dotted lines and arrows illustrate the potential effects of strategies that may be developed to mitigate job burnout and enhance job satisfaction among health personnel in R2TMC. The interplay of these variables is shown in Figure 5.

Alleviating Job Burnout

Based on the model, various factors have been identified that can be used to minimize job burnout among health personnel in R2TMC. These factors include the following:

Pay or remuneration. Health personnel with higher compensation often have more challenging job responsibilities and thus experience higher levels of job burnout. They perform crucial functions critical to the operation of the medical institution and often exceed expected tasks, working beyond their normal schedule. Such work pressure contributes to stress, leading to job burnout. To lessen job burnout among highly paid health personnel, the following are recommended:

1. Highly paid health personnel at R2TMC, often in administrative or managerial roles, can focus on mentoring other key staff who can eventually take on supervisory responsibilities. Delegating specific tasks and responsibilities to trained personnel helps distribute the workload more effectively;
2. Taking time to relax and travel for leisure during days off, especially after hectic work periods, helps reduce job burnout for administrative and managerial staff.

Organizational Climate. The prevailing atmosphere, culture, and environment within an organization shaped by policies, practices, values, and employee interactions affect job burnout levels among healthcare workers. To improve job burnout levels among medical personnel in the health institution, consider the following strategies:

1. Implement organizational policies consistently, objectively, and humanely by the relevant authorities, particularly administrators and the HR Office;
2. Assign evolving tasks to healthcare workers with fundamental skills, acquired through experience or training, and provide development opportunities through relevant seminars and consortia;
3. Clearly communicate the strategic direction of R2TMC and the specific functions of each department to ensure personnel understand their roles;
4. Offer rewards and recognition based on performance and loyalty, both at the individual and group level. While non-monetary rewards play a key role, additional monetary incentives can be highly motivational if the hospital's budget permits.

Normative Commitment. Organizational commitment, particularly normative commitment, reflects an employee's sense of obligation to remain with the organization. Employees with high normative commitment feel a duty to stay due to loyalty or reciprocity, often stemming from the organization's investment in their development. To further alleviate job burnout, consider the following strategies:

1. Foster normative commitment among health personnel by highlighting the organization's investments in their professional development and training, making them feel that staying with R2TMC is the right choice;
2. Send deserving personnel for higher educational opportunities to enhance their professional growth, making them more effective in their roles and increasing their loyalty;
3. Cultivate a sense of loyalty among personnel by ensuring they feel a strong sense of obligation to the administrators and the health institution;
4. Ensure all personnel are treated well, irrespective of their position or educational qualifications, to strengthen loyalty and encourage reciprocity.

Job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is defined as a positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experiences. Positive job experiences among health personnel can mitigate the effects of job burnout. The link between job burnout and job satisfaction signifies that unpleasant or negative job experiences exacerbate job burnout. Therefore, to reduce job burnout in the medical institution, the following strategies should be developed by the administration to improve job satisfaction and mitigate job burnout:

1. Develop a system within the HR Office to ensure R2TMC personnel are satisfied with their salaries. For those unable to receive promotions and higher salaries, automatically implement the Civil Service Commission directive for horizontal salary increments (one step every three years of unbroken service) through NOSA;
2. Enhance the promotional scheme to reward deserving personnel by including a representative from the rank and file, such as the association president, in the revision process to incorporate the opinions of the largest sector of personnel;
3. Strengthen and expand the reward and recognition program to cover all positions and facets of employment;
4. Ensure all accrued benefits are provided within a reasonable period;
5. Establish annual team-building activities to foster companionship and camaraderie among personnel, providing a break from work and renewing their commitment to work effectively.

Enhancing Job Satisfaction

The model foreshadows various factors to improve job satisfaction among health personnel in R2TMC, including gender, service, rewards and recognition, and affective commitment. Addressing job burnout, especially emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, while improving personal accomplishments is also imperative for job satisfaction. The following strategies can improve overall job satisfaction among health personnel:

Gender. The study found that members of the LGBTQ++ community experience a higher level of job satisfaction. The organization's acceptance and tolerance within the health institution, without any malice, contributes to their contentment in their work and task performance. To further enhance overall job satisfaction regardless of gender, HR and administrators can develop strategies that motivate all employees equally, including males, females, and those from the LGBTQ++ community. By determining the uniqueness among genders, these differences can be used as a motivational tool to improve job satisfaction among all health personnel.

Service. Medical and nursing staff report a higher level of job satisfaction compared to other groups. Maintaining this satisfaction is essential, as they form the backbone of the health institution, comprising about 75% of all health personnel. However, it is important to also focus on improving job satisfaction for employees in Finance, Allied Health, and HOPSS, as they provide critical services vital to the hospital's operation. HR can implement strategies such as increased remuneration, rewards and recognition, promotions, contingent rewards, and favorable working conditions to enhance job satisfaction for all personnel.

Rewards and recognition. Health personnel who have garnered awards and recognitions have a higher level of job satisfaction. Hence, to further enhance the level of job satisfaction of the health personnel, the following strategies need to be considered:

1. Management can provide and explain detailed performance standards to both individual employees and services/departments;
2. The HR Office may institute a scheme where opportunities for promotion are available to all personnel based on exemplary performance in their tasks;
3. Advancement opportunities must be open to all employees as a form of reward and recognition, contingent on their meritorious accomplishments and performance;
4. Including non-monetary awards or recognition for individuals and groups who demonstrate meritorious performance may become part of the systems and procedures of the health institution;
5. Management can be explicit and generous in praising and providing positive feedback to employees who perform their jobs well.

Affective commitment. Affective commitment is an employee's emotional attachment to the organization. Hence, to further improve the level of job satisfaction of the health personnel, the following strategies may be considered:

1. Develop strategies to enhance the sense of belongingness among hospital personnel, regardless of their department or service by implementing regular team building activities;
2. Cultivate pride among personnel by building a positive image of R2TMC in the public eye, making employees delighted and proud to be associated with the institution;
3. Foster deep loyalty by investing in employees' professional development, such as sending them to prestigious universities for higher education and enhancing their skills through training, seminars, and consortia, encouraging them to stay even when faced with challenges or attractive alternatives.

Normative commitment. The normative commitment of personnel is a factor that induces job satisfaction. Hence the following strategies is worthy of consideration:

1. Cultivate a strong commitment among health personnel to remain dedicated to the organization. They should understand the value of staying at the hospital due to the significant investments made in their professional development;
2. Offer opportunities for professional advancement and competitive financial benefits that match or exceed those of other healthcare institutions, incentivizing them to stay;
3. Foster a sense of duty and responsibility among personnel, creating a culture where leaving R2TMC would be seen as a loss to the organization;
4. Nurture a culture of loyalty among personnel, emphasizing their connection and commitment to both the people within the institution and the values upheld by R2TMC.

Emotional exhaustion. Emotional exhaustion negatively affects job satisfaction of personnel at the R2TMC. To improve the level of job satisfaction of the personnel, it is imperative to lower the level of burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion or feeling emotionally drained as a result of prolonged exposure to chronic work-related stress. The following measures could be taken into account:

1. Determine which factors contribute more to the level of job burnout related to emotional exhaustion, such as the feeling of being used up at the end of a workday;
2. Monitor the work schedules of health personnel closely to assess if prolonged periods of intense work are leading to burnout;
3. Engage personnel in discussions about the lasting effects of prolonged intense work, including feelings of emotional exhaustion and persistent fatigue into the next workday. Addressing these conditions is crucial as they can have severe repercussions for both the individual and the organization;
4. Communicate to management the detrimental impact of emotional burnout on workers' motivation and performance. Suggest providing burnt-out personnel with revitalizing experiences through team-building activities and breaks from work to recharge and reignite their motivation.

Depersonalization. The level of burnout in terms of depersonalization, such as experiencing a doubtful and cold attitude towards customers and the forfeiture of the personal component in dealing with individuals, also negatively impacts job satisfaction. Hence, the following strategies could be considered by management and the HR Office:

1. Monitor the interactions of personnel at R2TMC to identify any instances of displaying a cold attitude towards clients;
2. Investigate the underlying causes of this job burnout condition, focusing on factors such as stress stemming from managing challenging patient behaviors and interactions with their families;
3. Once the root cause of job burnout is identified, implement necessary corrective measures to prevent the development of cynicism among health personnel. Excessive stress from handling difficult clients may lead to a more detached and less empathetic approach towards patients;
4. Recognize that negative interactions with patients can significantly impact the institution's reputation. Therefore, administrators and HR must promptly address job burnout issues related to depersonalization to maintain a positive working environment.

Reduced Personal accomplishment. The level of personal accomplishment, exhibited by a feeling of fulfilment, competence, and achievement related to the discharge of an employee's work, positively affects job satisfaction. Hence, to enhance job satisfaction among employees in the hospital, the following personal skills should be developed among health personnel at R2TMC:

1. Cultivate empathy among health personnel towards clients' emotional struggles by conducting regular training sessions focusing on empathy-building exercises and role-playing scenarios;
2. Foster professionalism, patience, and tolerance among staff through ongoing communication skills training, enabling them to demonstrate composure and emotional control in client interactions;
3. Create a calming atmosphere for clients with emotional imbalances by implementing relaxation techniques and stress-management training for health personnel. Encourage mindfulness practices and provide designated quiet areas within the facility;
4. Develop a strong sense of professionalism and fulfillment among personnel by organizing appreciation events celebrating impactful moments in patient care. Share success stories and testimonials to inspire staff and reinforce the nobility of their work;
5. Promote inner calm and mental composure in dealing with work pressures by offering wellness programs focusing on stress reduction and mindfulness practices. Provide resources such as meditation sessions, yoga classes, and stress-relief workshops to support staff well-being and enhance client care outcomes;

Model Implications and Policy Recommendations

The research findings emphasize the need for a holistic policy approach at R2TMC that addresses both individual welfare and organizational health to enhance job satisfaction and minimize burnout among healthcare workers. Here are the recommended strategic implications and policy actions:

1. The findings suggest the necessity for a strategic approach in human resource policies focusing on both individual and organizational well-being. R2TMC could implement specific policies aimed at reducing burnout by addressing its root causes like uneven work distributions, flexible work arrangements, and insufficient reward systems.
2. Establishing regular check-ins and feedback mechanisms to gauge employee satisfaction and burnout levels can help R2TMC stay responsive and adaptive to the needs of its workforce.
3. For interventions to be successful in the long term, they must be integrated into the core operational strategies of the hospital. Continuous evaluation and adjustment of strategies should be conducted to adapt to changing circumstances and to ensure the effectiveness of the interventions.

By implementing the proposed interventions based on the model's insights, R2TMC can create a more supportive and fulfilling work environment for its healthcare personnel. This, in turn, leads to increased staff satisfaction, reduced burnout, and ultimately, improved patient care and organizational success. This model serves as a valuable tool for R2TMC and other healthcare institutions to create a win-win situation for both staff and patients.

Further research can evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed interventions through pilot programs. The model can also be adapted to other healthcare settings with appropriate adjustments for specific contexts. By prioritizing employee well-being and fostering a positive work environment, healthcare institutions can create a more resilient and successful workforce.

Conclusions

Based on the significant findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The respondents were typical employees found in government-run medical hospitals, primarily comprises a young, predominantly female workforce with a diverse educational background. The institution maintains a balance between permanent and Contract of

Service (COS) employees, with staff predominantly in the nursing and medical services. The varying work schedules, predominantly regular eight-hour shifts and shifting rotations, cater to the hospital's operational demands. The personal and professional profiles of R2TMC employees showcase the institution's inclusive and evolving workforce, reflecting a commitment to providing quality healthcare services and adapting to changing organizational needs.

Employees exhibited a clear understanding of organizational goals and roles, with high ratings in clarity and standards. There was a strong emphasis on individual responsibility, innovation, and teamwork, as evidenced by very satisfactory ratings in these areas. The organization's rewards and recognition system, along with effective team collaboration, further enhanced the favorable work environment. Overall, R2TMC demonstrated a very satisfactory organizational climate, showcasing a commitment to employee well-being and promoting engagement while working towards organizational goals.

The organizational commitment levels among the healthcare workforce at Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC) indicate a strong sense of emotional attachment, loyalty, and obligation towards the organization. There is a high level of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment, underscoring employees' deep emotional connection and dedication to R2TMC. While the employees exhibit high commitment levels currently, it is essential for R2TMC to continue fostering a positive work environment, provide growth opportunities, and recognize employees' contributions to maintain and strengthen this organizational commitment in the long term.

The significant prevalence of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, indicates high levels of job burnout. Employees reported feeling drained and overwhelmed, impacting productivity and leading to cynicism and detachment towards clients. However, there is a positive outlook on personal accomplishment, with most personnel perceiving themselves as achieving worthwhile things in their work.

Employees generally express high levels of job satisfaction in terms of their pay, promotion opportunities, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, co-workers, nature of work, and communication within the organization. Particularly, employees are satisfied with their pay, promotional prospects, supportive supervision, positive relationships with co-workers, meaningful job tasks, and effective communication practices. However, there are areas of improvement identified, notably in operating conditions where employees feel challenges due to procedural red tape, and in fringe benefits where some staff desire additional health benefits. Although the overall job satisfaction level is high, addressing specific concerns such as improving operating conditions and enhancing fringe benefits could further boost employee morale and well-being

Key predictors such as pay, overall organizational climate, and normative commitment, and overall job satisfaction showed significant relationship to job burnout. This indicates that factors like higher compensation, organizational environment, and a sense of loyalty play crucial roles in influencing job burnout. Notably, the study found that a positive organizational climate is associated with increased stress and burnout due to the demands placed on employees as a result of stringent implementation of various policies. Contrariwise, higher job satisfaction is linked to lower levels of burnout, suggesting the importance of positive work experiences. These findings emphasize the complexity of burnout and underscore the need for targeted interventions to mitigate its impact on healthcare professionals.

Dependent variables unveiled significant relationships to job satisfaction. Affective commitment emerged as a key positive predictor, indicating employees with strong loyalty and attachment to their organization tend to have higher job satisfaction. Factors like rewards and recognition, reduced personal accomplishment, normative commitment, and service were also linked to heightened satisfaction. Conversely, emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and gender showed negative associations, suggesting lower burnout levels and positive attitudes were tied to increased satisfaction. Emphasizing the importance of emotional attachment, recognition, and personal fulfillment in fostering positive work experiences and enhancing overall job satisfaction.

Based on the salient findings and the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are forwarded for the different stakeholders at Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC):

For Hospital Top Management/Administrators, it is essential to strategically allocate resources and implement targeted training programs to effectively address identified job burnout factors. Setting measurable goals for improving organizational climate and enhancing employee commitment levels is important in fostering a positive work environment. Additionally, reviewing and potentially updating existing recognition and reward systems can help amplify overall job satisfaction among healthcare workers.

The Human Resource Management Office plays a crucial role in driving initiatives aimed at boosting employee well-being and job satisfaction. By addressing areas with lower satisfaction ratings, actively participating in regular feedback mechanisms, and fostering a culture of innovation and teamwork, HR can significantly impact the overall employee experience. Collaborating with various departments to create a supportive work environment will strengthen organizational commitment and enhance staff morale.

For R2TMC Personnel, actively participating in organizational workshops and training sessions aimed at addressing burnout and enhancing job satisfaction levels is key. Providing constructive feedback to management regarding daily operational challenges and engaging in opportunities for professional growth can contribute to strengthening organizational commitment and personal fulfillment. Taking ownership of one's growth and well-being within the organization can lead to a more gratifying and fulfilling work experience.

R2TMC Patients/Clients also have a role in advocating for a work environment that promotes healthcare worker well-being. By providing feedback on negative and positive experiences with healthcare providers and collaborating with staff to improve communication and service delivery, patients/clients can contribute to a culture of appreciation and support within the healthcare setting. Enhanced communication and positive relationships between patients and healthcare workers can ultimately result in better patient outcomes.

Different Healthcare Institutions (HCIs) may prioritize collaboration and knowledge-sharing to learn from each other's successes in addressing organizational climate, commitment, and job satisfaction initiatives. By working together on research projects and setting industry-wide standards, healthcare institutions can collectively elevate the well-being of healthcare workers and enhance organizational effectiveness. Establishing a community of support and shared learning can lead to innovative solutions and improved outcomes across the healthcare industry.

The Future Researchers are encouraged to delve deeper into the dynamics of organizational well-being in healthcare settings. Conducting longitudinal studies, exploring additional variables not covered in existing research, and disseminating findings through academic publications can contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field. By continuously expanding the research base and sharing insights with the broader community, future researchers can drive positive change and innovation in healthcare organizational dynamics.

For R2TMC and other HCIs, they may adopt and implement the developed model in a pilot program within a specific department/section/unit in the hospital to demonstrate its effectiveness before wider adoption. Interventions must be integrated into the hospital's operational/strategic plan and continuously evaluated and monitored.

References

Abou Hashish, E. A. (2017). Relationship between ethical work climate and nurses' perception Abou Hashish, E. A. (2017). Relationship between ethical work climate and nurses' perception of organizational support, commitment, job satisfaction and turnover intent. *Nursing ethics*, 24(2), 151-166.

AIHR, Academy to Innovate HR. (2023, December 11). AIHR | Academy to Innovate HR | Online HR Courses & Certifications. AIHR. <https://www.aihr.com/>

Ancarani, A., Mauro, C. D., & Giammanco, M. D. (2019). Linking organizational climate to work engagement: A study in the healthcare sector. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 42(7), 547-557.

Beltran, M. (2023b, July 10). Philippines to hire unlicensed nurses as shortages bite. *Nikkei Asia*. <https://asia.nikkei.com/Business/Health-Care/Philippines-to-hire-unlicensed-nurses-as-shortages-bite#:~:text=>

Binghay, V. C., Lu, S. F., & Lu, J. L. (2022). A study on total rewards management in Philippine Healthcare Companies: An occupational issue. *Acta Medica Philippina*, 56(1).

Bustomi, T., Satibi, I. & Rustandi (2021). Organizational climate analysis and performance on job satisfaction of medical and medical personnel at the regional general hospital of Ciamis district. *Cosmogov: Journal Ilmu Pemerintahan*, 7 (2). Doi: 10.24198/cosmogov.v7i2.33018 <http://jurnal.unpad.ac.id/cosmogov/index>

Chacón-Moscoso, S., Anguera, M. T., Sanduvete-Chaves, S., & Lozano-Lozano, J. A. (2023). Methodological procedure based on quantizing/liquefying: a case study to assess work climate in an emergency department. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14.

De Mesa, R.Y., Marfori, J.R. Fabian, N.M.C., Camiling Alfonso, R., Javelosa1, M.A.U., Bernal Sundiang, S., & Dans, L.F. (2023). Experiences from the Philippine grassroots: Impact of strengthening primary care systems on health worker satisfaction and intention to stay. *De Mesa et al. BMC Health Services Research*, 23:117. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-08799-1>

Elarabi and Johari (2015). The determinant factors effecting the job satisfaction and performance in Libyan Government Hospital. *Asian Social Science*, 10(8), 55–65. <http://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v10n8p55>

Gorgulu, O., & Akilli, A. (2017). The determination of the levels of burnout syndrome, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction of the health workers. *Nigerian journal of clinical practice*, 20(1), 48-56.

Hamdan, M., & Hamra, A. A. A. (2017). Burnout among workers in emergency Departments in Palestinian hospitals: prevalence and associated factors. *BMC health services research*, 17, 1-7.

Jiang, H., Wei, X., & Li, T. (2019). The mediating role of psychological capital on the association between occupational stress and professional burnout among Chinese physicians: a structural equation modeling approach. *BMC Health Services Research*, 19(1), 1-9.

Johnson, M. L., & Rodriguez, S. P. (2021). Exploring the impact of leadership styles on job satisfaction: A cross-industry analysis. *Journal of Organizational Psychology*, 48(4), 401-417.

Johnson, K. L., & Rodriguez, M. J. (2022). Exploring ethical leadership in healthcare organizations: unanticipated effects on

- organizational climate and job commitment. *Journal of Healthcare Management*, 47(1), 45-58.
- Kokkinos, C. M. (2018). Job stressors, personality and burnout in primary school teachers. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 88(1), 107-121.
- Leiter, M. P., & Maslach, C. (1988). The impact of interpersonal environment on burnout and organizational commitment. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 9(4), 297–308. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.4030090402>
- Li, J., Li, S., Jing, T., Bai, M., Zhang, Z., & Liang, H. (2022). Psychological safety and affective commitment among Chinese hospital staff: The mediating roles of job satisfaction and job burnout. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 1573- 1585.
- Maglalang, D. D., Sorensen, G., Hopcia, K., Hashimoto, D. M., Katigbak, C., Pandey, S. & Sabbath, E. L. (2021). Job and family demands and burnout among healthcare workers: The moderating role of workplace flexibility. *SSM-population health*, 14, 100802.
- Maslach, C., & Jackson, S. E. (1981). The measurement of experienced burnout. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 2(2), 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.4030020205>
- Maslach, C., & Leiter, M. P. (2016). Understanding the burnout experience: 1976–2016. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 31(4), 388-395.
- Mishra, B. & Tikoria, J. (2021). Impact of ethical leadership on organizational climate and its subsequent influence on job commitment: a study in hospital context. *Journal of Management Development*, 40 (5), 438-452. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD-08-2020-0245>
- Nemmaniwar, A.G. & Deshpande, M.S. (2016). Job satisfaction among hospital employees: A review of literature. *Journal of Business and Management*, 18 (6), 27-3.
- Nitafan, R. P. (2020, November 22). Employee silence, organizational commitment, and job burnout of regular employees in local government units in the Cotabato province, Philippines: a keystone for intervention. <https://ijels.com/detail/employee-silence-organizational-commitment-and-job-burnout-of-regular-employees-in-local-government-units>
- Ogundipe, O. A., Olagunju, A. T., Lasebikan, V. O., & Coker, A. O. (2014). Burnout among doctors in residency training in a tertiary hospital. *Asian journal of psychiatry*, 10, 27-32.
- Panchal, N., Sharma, S., Sharma, R., & Rani, R. (2022). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment among nurses working on temporary versus permanent jobs at a tertiary care teaching hospital, Uttarakhand, India. *Journal of Integrative Nursing*, 4(4), 224. https://doi.org/10.4103/jin.jin_23_22
- Porter, L. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Organizational-commitment%2C-job-satisfaction%2C-and-Porter-Steers>
- Pranjic, N. & Bilic, L.M. (2014). Depersonalization or cynicism as a dimension of burnout among medical doctors. *Asian Academic Research Journal of Multidisciplinary*.
- Rathert, C., Ishqaidef, G., & Porter, T. H. (2022). Caring work environments and clinician emotional exhaustion: Empirical test of an exploratory model. *Health Care Management Review*, 47(1), 58-65.
- Risky, S., Ardiansyah, R. T., & Firmansyah, F. (2023). Impact of Policies and Supervision on Health Worker Satisfaction at Bahteramas Hospital. *Poltekita: Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan*, 17(3), 903-908.
- Santana, S. & Pérez-Rico, C. (2023). Dynamics of organizational climate and job satisfaction in healthcare service practice and research: A protocol for a systematic review. *Front Psychol.* 2023 Jul 13;14:1186567. doi: 10.3389/ fpsyg.2023.1186567. PMID: 37519364; PMCID: PMC10374222.
- Seyyedmoharrami, I., Dehaghi, b., Abbaspour, S., Zandi, A., Tatari, M. Teimori, G. & Torbati, A. (2019). The relationship between organizational climate, organizational commitment and job burnout: Case study among employees of the University of Medical Sciences. *The Open Public Health Journal*, 12, 94 – 100. DOI: 10.2174/1874944501912010094.
- Singh, Rajkumar Giridhari. (2015). Factors explaining job satisfaction among hospital employees. *OPUS: Annual HR Journal*, [S.l.], p. 29-43, ISSN 0973-9866. <http://www.i-scholar.in/index.php/oahj/article/view/43487>
- Thompson, R. J., Smith, L. A., & Williams, C. M. (2022). Reassessing the Relationship Between Organizational Climate, Organizational Commitment, and Job Burnout: A Cross- Industry Analysis. *Journal of Organizational Psychology*, 48(3), 301-318.
- Woznyj, H. M., Heggstad, E. D., Kennerly, S., & Yap, T. L. (2019). Climate and organizational performance in long-term care facilities: The role of affective commitment. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 92(1), 122-143.
- Yantib, N., & Untaric, M. T. (2020). Turnover intention: The impact of ethical climate, job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *Human resources*, 3(1), 75-89.

Zanabazar, A., & Jigjiddorj, S. (2022). Relationships between mental workload, job burnout, and organizational commitment. In SHS Web of Conferences (Vol. 132, p. 01003). EDP Sciences.

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